

Reaction of the Mixture of Thiosulphate and Nitrite with Mineral Acids

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The acid requirement of mixtures of thiosulphate and nitrite for complete decomposition has been investigated potentiometrically and found to change with experimental conditions. The results show that the reactions involved are complex and may involve simple displacement of thiosulphuric and nitrous acids, followed by autoxidations of the free acids, their atmospheric oxidations, or oxidation by nitrous acid.

Little attention appears to have been devoted to a reaction of the mixture of thiosulphate and nitrite with mineral acids. According to Falciola¹, if a solution containing sodium thiosulphate and sodium nitrite is made faintly acidic by addition of a mineral acid, or an organic acid, or even alum, enough nitrous acid and thiosulphuric acid are liberated to enter into the reaction. A yellow, green, or brown colour is produced, depending on the concentration. He even suggested that the reaction might be used for testing either thiosulphate or nitrite ions qualitatively. According to Gutmann², sodium thiosulphate does not act on a cold or boiling solution of sodium nitrite. In a sealed tube at 100°, a mixture of nitrite and calcium thiosulphate reacts:

Abel³ observed that the titration of iodine and thiosulphate did not proceed in the usual manner in presence of nitrite, but involved a deficit of thiosulphate in which he considered the following reactions were involved:

Sorum⁴ also studied the kinetics of the reaction of thiosulphate and nitrite in dilute aqueous acid. Reactions for the formation of hexathionate from thiosulphate, nitrite, and HCl have also been discussed by using radioactive sulphur and probable mechanisms⁵ have been suggested. From the study of the iodine-thiosulphate reaction in presence of nitrite, Abel⁶ has suggested the mechanism involving the reaction of NO^+ with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$.

In our previous investigations⁷ in which we studied the behaviour of mineral acids (HCl , H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , and HClO_4) towards nitrite solutions, we have established the following two processes :

1. *Gazzetta*, 1922, 52, 179.

2. "Über den Abhan der Thiosulphate und einiger Polyionate zu Sulfiten durch reduzierende Salze in alkalischer Lösung und über engie Monosulfoxyarsenate", München, 1897.

3. *Monatsh.*, 1950, 81, 7.

4. Thesis, Univ. of Wisconsin.

5. *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 14459d.

6. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1957, 292, 242.

7. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 155 and unpublished work.

We have further found that reaction (ii) appears only when the mixture is acidic or the initial concentration of nitrite is large. In attempting to extend these investigations to sodium thiosulphate, when this substance was titrated with mineral acids, using a bright platinum electrode indicator, no inflection was observed on the titration curve. We then thought it to be of interest to use mixtures of nitrite and thiosulphate in place of pure thiosulphate.

Apparently, there is no indication of a direct reaction between NaNO_2 and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ in complete absence of an acid. Preliminary experiments, however, indicated that a distinct chemical reaction, different from thiosulphate-mineral acid reaction, took place when a mixture of nitrite and thiosulphate was acidified with mineral or acetic acid. The reaction is visually observable due to formation of a yellow or greenish colour in the first instance, which soon vanishes and the solution acquires a white turbidity due to separation of sulphur. For the same amount of thiosulphate, the amount of sulphur precipitated appears to depend on the relative amount of sodium nitrite present. When no sodium nitrite is present, the amount of sulphur precipitated is large; as the nitrite concentration is increased, it is comparatively much small.

A systematic study of this reaction through potentiometric titrations was therefore undertaken. This method deals with equilibrium mixtures produced after each addition of the reagent and not very much with the rates of reactions going on in the cell, but eliminates elaborate analytical procedures of doubtful value. A mixture of nitrite and thiosulphate was taken in the cell and the acid added from a burette. Reverse titration, i.e., with nitrite + acid or thiosulphate + acid in the cell, was not possible for obvious reasons. Titrations were performed using HCl and H_2SO_4 . In the first instance, a few titrations were performed with mixtures of nitrite and thiosulphate of different dilutions (from $N/10$ to $N/100$) in order to ascertain any effect due to dilutions. Results in Table I hardly suggest any such effect. When the solutions in the cell were very dilute (less than $0.025N$), the yellowish green colour, first formed by addition of acid, was found to vanish without any visible separation of sulphur.

EXPERIMENTAL

Titrations were performed with a fixed amount of NaNO_2 and varying amounts of thiosulphate and *vice versa*. As an inert atmosphere plays an important part in the behaviour of HNO_2 , some of the titrations were repeated in an atmosphere of CO_2 .

Every time, when the acid was added from the burette, the solution on shaking acquired a yellowish or greenish colour which soon disappeared with the appearance of a white turbidity. When a sufficient amount of acid had been added to correspond to the point of inflection in the curve, such turbidity did not appear any further. Stable readings on the potentiometer could not be recorded unless one waited 40 to 50 minutes after the addition of acid from the burette. The results are summarised in Tables I to VI. Some titration graphs are reproduced in Fig. 1 and 2.

HCl (ml) →
 FIG. 1 (vide Table I).
 (Co-ordinates are independent)

HCl (ml) →
 FIG. 2 (vide Table V)

TABLE I

In air.
 V ml of xN - Na_2NO_2 + V' ml of xN - $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ ($f=1.004$) in cell, yN -HCl in burette.

V.	V'	x.	y.	Infection.	N-HCl		Curve No.
					Used up	Reqd.	
10	10	0.10	0.83	1.50	1.245	1.167	I
20	20	0.050	0.83	1.50	1.245	1.167	II
10	10	0.050	0.83	0.75	0.627	0.583	III
10	10	0.025	0.25	1.25	1.250	1.167	IV
20	20	0.0125	0.25	1.25	1.250	1.167	V

TABLE II

In air.
 10 ml of $N/10$ - NaNO_2 + V ml of $N/10$ - $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ ($f = 0.99$) in cell.
 $1.005 N$ -HCl in burette.

V.	HCl used up.	HCl reqd.	Curve No.
5	0.65	0.91	I
6	0.75	0.96	II
7	0.85	1.01	III
8	0.95	1.06	IV
9	1.10	1.11	V
10	1.20	1.16	VI
12	1.40	1.26	VII

TABLE III

*In air.*10 ml of $N/10\text{-Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ ($f=0.99$) + V ml of $N/10\text{-NaNO}_2$ in cell. 1.005 $N\text{-HCl}$ in burette.

V.	HCl used up.	HCl required.	Curve No.
0	No infection	..	..
1	"	..	..
2	"	..	..
3	"	..	..
4	1.2 ml	0.767 ml	I
5	1.2	0.834	II
8	1.2	1.034	III
10	1.2	1.167	
14	1.2	1.434	IV
20	1.2	1.830	V

TABLE IV

In air. V ml of $N/10\text{-NaNO}_2$ + V' ml $N/10\text{-Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ ($f=0.99$) in cell. 1.012 $N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ in burette.

V.	V'.	H_2SO_4 used up.	H_2SO_4 required.	Curve No.
4.5	10	1.2 ml	0.834 ml	I
10	10	1.2	1.167	II
10	5	0.6	0.910	III
2	10	No infection	..	..
0	10	do	..	..

TABLE V

*In CO_2 atmosphere.*10 ml of $N/10\text{-NaNO}_2$ + V ml of $N/10\text{-Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ ($f = 0.985$) in cell. $xN\text{-HCl}$ added from burette.

V.	x.	HCl used up.	N-HCl		Curve No.
			Required.	Found.	
5	1.01	0.8 ml	0.91	0.808 ml	I
6	0.83	1.1	0.96	0.913	II
8	1.01	1.2	1.06	1.212	III
10	0.83	1.8	1.16	1.490	IV
12	1.01	1.8	1.26	1.1818	V

TABLE VI

*In CO_2 atmosphere.*10 ml of $N/10\text{-Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ ($f=0.985$) + V ml of $N/10\text{-NaNO}_2$ in cell. 1.01 $N\text{-HCl}$ in burette.

V.	Acid used up.	HCl required (N).	HCl found (N).	Curve No.
5	No Infection	..	..	
7	"	..	..	
8	1.45 ml	1.034 ml	1.46 ml	VI
10	(As in Table V)			
14	1.45	1.434	1.46	VII

DISCUSSION

Table III records a minimum value of ratio of NaNO_2 to thiosulphate for the titration to be feasible. Above this critical ratio, the point of inflection always corresponds to 1.2 ml so long as the amount of thiosulphate remains the same (10 ml, $N/1$). This critical ratio is raised when the titration is carried out in an atmosphere of CO_2 (Table VI). The amount of acid consumed is increased at the same time. On the other hand, when the amount of NaNO_2 is fixed and that of thiosulphate varied (Tables II, V), the amount of acid consumed varies; but in no case is an equivalence or any kind of stoichiometry to be found between the two. The amount of acid consumed is always greater than what is required for the thiosulphate alone on account of simple stoichiometry.

If we assume that mineral acids react with thiosulphate in the same way as they do with nitrite, *i.e.*, thiosulphuric acid is displaced in the first instance followed by reactions (i) and (ii) (autoxidation and air oxidation) depending on circumstances, a number of results may be predicted in the experiments reported in the above tables.

The *required* values shown in the tables above have been calculated on the basis that the acid requirement of nitrite equals two thirds of the total amount of nitrite (justified because the mixture is neutral, *vide supra*) (reaction i) and that of thiosulphate is one-half of its own amount,

the other half of mineral acid coming from autoxidation of thiosulphuric acid or perhaps from oxidation by nitrous acid. This oxidation is not unlikely. We have definitely demonstrated it when nitrite is present. The data for acid required in Table II have been calculated thus. The total nitrite is 10 ml of $N/10$, so that with reaction (i) in view, acid required = 0.66 ml of N ; when the total thiosulphate = 12 ml of $N/10$, acid required = 0.6 ml of N on the basis of reactions just stated, *viz.*, (iii a) and (iii b). The total acid requirement therefore = 1.26 ml against 1.4 ml found. We find that there is some parallelism between the figures calculated here and those actually observed. At a particular ratio of nitrite to thiosulphate, *viz.*, 9:10 (or even 10:10), there is a very close agreement between the calculated and observed values. On changing the ratio in favour of nitrite, *i.e.*, by decreasing the amount of thiosulphate, the acid requirement decreases and on changing the ratio in favour of thiosulphate, the acid requirement increases. We may explain this on the basis of three basic ideas, *viz.*, simple displacement reaction, reaction (i), and reaction (ii). When acid consumption is less, both reactions (i) and (ii) may be operative with (ii) preponderating. Increasing the quantity of thiosulphate favours reaction (i), or even simple displacement to some extent. We actually find that in the example cited above, the acid consumed is 1.4 ml as against 1.26 ml required, whereas for the simple displacement, the requirement would be 3.0 ml.

Some of the experiments reported in Table III are independent repetitions of those reported in Table II, *viz.*, those in which the volumes of nitrite used are 20, 10, and 5 ml. We find that the observed acid requirements check fairly well in the two tables. We conclude therefore that the constancy of the acid requirement in Table III is explicable in the same manner as we have explained the results in Table II. The constancy, we feel, is fortuitous. There are a number of complex processes behind it.

Tables V and VI show that when air is excluded, the acid requirement increases. There is approximately 25% increase in acid consumption. This means that relative speeds of reactions (i) and (ii) are altered in favour of reaction (i) or even simple displacement.

Incidentally, in complete absence of thiosulphate, when nitrite was titrated with HCl or H_2SO_4 , we had no indication of reaction (ii). We are therefore led to conclude that it is the presence of thiosulphuric acid which initiates reaction (ii) in much the same way as HNO_3 does. The suppression of reaction (ii) by increasing amounts of thiosulphate, however, may be due to some independent reaction between free HNO_2 and thiosulphuric acid, leading to a nearly complete destruction of HNO_2 , as was reported earlier⁷, when potassium iodide or urea was used in place of thiosulphate.

We feel that the reactions investigated here are very interesting and shall receive our further attention in due course. We intend to devise experiments which may settle the extents of reactions (i), (ii), (iii), and a simple displacement.

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